

VIDEO-BASED TASK TEACHING FOR NON-ENGLISH MAJOR STUDENTS AT HUFU

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ABSTRACT

The teaching and learning English process can be facilitated by different interesting and engaging activities at HUFU, among which listening comprehension through authentic videos has been almost carried out in the courses of all levels from A1 to B2. However, little research has been conducted to investigate the effects of teaching listening through video-based tasks in the classroom as an extensive supporting tool to enhance the listening skill among non-English major students at HUFU. As a result, this study aims to explore the process and products of video-based tasks. The data were collected through questionnaires and interviews. A set of questionnaires was delivered to forty students in the English course A2 class after the listening learning process through six video-based task performances in the classroom to figure out how using videos motivated their listening learning. Moreover, the researcher carried out interviews of five students to double-check their evaluation of applying video-based task in English listening learning. The findings indicated that the students showed positive feedback on videos because they felt more interested and motivated.

Keywords: video-based tasks; listening comprehension; student-centeredness; motivation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The teaching of English as a second language (EFL) has been focused and changed positively at HUFU for the recent years and more importantly the aim to help students significantly improve their English communication skill in the real contexts has been more and more emphasized. However, there has been a limited success and existed a lot of challenges where students still face not being competent in English skills, especially in their listening skills. It is actually believed that students are expected to make a lot of efforts, concentration and determination during the process of English listening learning. In fact, researchers concluded the undeniable reasons of being necessary to be competent in English listening. Underwood (1989) stated that listening is a naturally obtained process in learning a new language and through the listening process learners gain a large amount of oral input beforehand. Moreover, a good speaker must be a good listener; hence, Krashen (1989) asserted that listening comprehension offers suitable conditions for language competence.

Regarding the practice of English listening skill, learners can apply a variety of techniques; however, choosing an effective way to facilitate listening skill is hard stuff that most of the non-English major students at HUFU have been facing meanwhile there have existed a diversified range of listening sources in the current era of Internet overwhelming. Choosing suitable and effective materials to teach students' English listening becomes a pretty crucial and challenging duty that

each teacher of English needs to pay attention because this demonstrates a reliable teaching method.

As a result, in English courses for non-English major students at HUFU, apart from audios with designed tasks used to teach listening skill in the classrooms, teachers can take advantage of supporting videos in the course textbooks as well as chosen videos from the Youtube channel of National Geographic as an extensive source for assisting students to develop their English listening ability. Apparently, videos materials as a valuable supporting teaching aid can be connected with audio materials in listening lessons since they possess a rich source of communicating situations by native speakers all over the world. According to former researchers, videos bring a lot of undeniable benefits in mastering English, so they are widely used as a reliable instrument in EFL classrooms.

For mentioned reasons, the researcher carried this study to explore the students' evaluation of applying video-based tasks in the English listening learning and teaching process in an EFL classroom at HUFU.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Extensive listening

As defined, listening skill can be classified into two types based on different listening approaches including intensive and extensive listening. According to Harmer (2001), a mix of both methods can boost learners' listening ability. However, some research showed that teachers paid a bit attention to extensive learning materials in spite of its considerable values in order to support better students in listening comprehension.

According to Waring (2010), extensive listening is to raise listening fluency and improve listening speed, which contributes to students' ability to understand what they are listening to at their certain listening level. Renandya and Farrell (2011) made clear that extensive listening possesses all kinds of listening activities to encourage students to achieve comprehensive and exciting input, resulting in pleasure in listening learning providing that listening materials must be purposeful enough for learners to achieve something from it.

Moreover, Renandya (2011) stated that the good factors of extensive listening on second language learning consist of boosting learners' ability to handle the speech rate and vocabulary recognition skill, enriching vocabulary and making them listening more comprehensively. As stated by Vo (2013:30), learners may select any listening materials that are fit and enjoyable for them; for example, they can choose their favorite radio or television programs for daily listening practice to have pleasure and improve general language.

Authentic videos in teaching language

It is necessary for teachers to choose meaningful and helpful materials to enhance students' language learning based on factors like the goals of each course; among these materials are authentic videos, which have been brought a lot of benefits not only for in-class lessons but also for self-study at home.

William & Lutes (2003) highlighted the importance of videos; that is they can help with stuff that cannot be ready in a traditional classroom such as access to native language speakers in a variety of natural situations. Additionally, authentic videos are considered as a combination of visual and

aural information; hence, employing them in listening lessons can enable learners to absorb more knowledge because learners can listen and see materials simultaneously.

In fact, Harmer (2001) claimed that “Video is richer than audio: speakers can be seen; their body movements give clues as to meaning; so do the clothes they wear, their location, etc.” Background details can be supplied visually. Also, it is advantageous that videos comprise visual clues such as gestures, emotions or non-verbal behaviors, well supporting learners’ comprehension and helping learners interpret the video in a deeper way. Obviously, learners can analyze language easily and flexibly thanks to connections between words and images during the process of watching videos.

Moreover, Köksal (2004) showed some good factors of applying videos in language such as drawing learners’ concentration, being applicable in a crowded class, offering learners a variety of words, providing a real communication context, motivating learners’ discussion and oral comprehension, developing learners’ imagination, and facilitating long-term memory thanks to auditory, visible and mental links.

In order to add some more advantages of using videos in language pedagogy, Ting Hung (2009) also mentioned that authentic videos can create autonomous learners and develop students’ critical thinking skill. As a result, learners are partly more active in their EFL process.

3 METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted during the English course A1, included in the four-course EFL program from A1 to B2 for non-English major students at Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry. In this course, the target students were expected to achieve a proficiency English level which is equivalent to the A1 according to the Standards of the Vietnamese Framework for English reference level. The students aged from 18 to 20 were the freshmen of various fields including Information Technology, Tourism, Food Technology, Accounting and Banking.

To collect the data, the researcher (as the in-charge teacher) decided to set up two sets of questionnaires for the target students. Firstly, the teacher directly guided her forty students in listening skill through video-based tasks. In particular, the target students spent every about thirty minutes watching and doing tasks on one of six in-class videos, which took place continuously during six weeks. Besides, the teacher also offered six more videos for them to watch at home and asked them to give ideas or comments on each video to demonstrate their listening comprehension some days later. The topics of videos were based on units in the course book namely LIFE (Pre-Intermediate, National Geographic Learning by CENGAGE Publisher). These topics consisted of journeys, appearance, films and the art, science, tourism, and the Earth.

In the next phase, the teacher would deliver the other set of questionnaires to evaluate how the video-based task performance could motivate the students’ listening learning. Moreover, interviews were given to five immediate students including open-ended questions to gain comments on the students’ experience and evaluation of the whole process.

Finally, the findings collected from questionnaires and interviews would be synthesized and analyzed. The researcher applied the Excel worksheet to measure and compared the students’ responses.

4 FINDINGS

The below table illustrates the percentages of students who were expected to respond on their point of view of using videos in their English listening skill. From the table it can be seen that there is a positive view on using videos as a source of English listening, with the significant majority of students who agreed with each item although there are still a moderately large portion of students giving no ideas in almost all aspects.

For the first point, an extremely large portion of participants agreed that they prefer using videos as an English listening material to audio materials, with 82.5%, and 17.5% among these respondents strongly agreed with this idea. On the contrary, there is no one neglecting the preference of using videos as a listening tool. In addition, well over a half of the students were interested in learning English thanks to video-based tasks in classroom although over 7% of the students did not show interest in studying through videos and nearly 28% had no responses to this factor.

As the aspect of motivation that videos can bring to the students is figured out, there are an approximately considerable number of students with 52.5% who claimed that they were motivated to listen to the target language after classroom through given videos by the teacher. Besides, only a small portion of students disagreed with the statement at about 7%, and it is surprising that a rather high number of about 32% of the students had no ideas on the motivation of videos in listening at home. Next, for the videos' benefit of enhancing students' listening comprehension, the considerable percentage of the students showing strong agreement is well over 60% whereas no students ignored this benefit of videos.

Moreover, highly significant numbers of respondents agreed that guided images and key words of the captions for videos inspired them a lot and also that English subtitles in each video were very helpful, with roughly 70% and 80% respectively. Only 5% of the students did not find videos' photos and captions inspiring them.

With regards to the provided videos' interesting and lively features, just below 40% of the students supported this. Meanwhile, compared with other items, a much larger portion of the students did not admit this idea, with 15%. Similarly, the percentages of disagreeing students are 10% and 15% where the use of videos in practicing English in the real contexts and developing student's critical thinking skill is concerned. On the other hand, more than 60% agreed that videos facilitated the students to practice English in the real world, and 45% said that their critical thinking skill was enhanced through videos.

In the case of learning vocabulary, no students ignored the benefits of watching videos in enhancing vocabulary ranges and the ability of memorizing new words. Well over three quarters of the students agreed that their vocabulary capacity increased a lot after watching videos. Moreover, just over a half mentioned that they could remember English words without many difficulties through video-based tasks.

When asked about whether students' learned English with supplied videos at home or not, a significant number of respondents, with well over two thirds, agreed with that. The number of students rejecting practicing English with given videos at home was nearly the same as those with no ideas, with about 10%.

Table: Findings on the evaluation of students in English listening learning through video-based materials

Evaluation items	Strongly disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly agree (%)	No idea (%)
1 I prefer using videos as an English listening material to audio materials.	0	0	82.5	17.5	0
2 I become interested in learning English as the teacher uses English videos in classroom.	5	0	12.5	55	27.5
3 I am motivated to listen to English outside the classroom thanks to provided videos by the teacher.	2.5	5	52.5	7.5	32.5
4 Videos enhance my listening comprehension.	0	0	62.5	15	22.5
5 Guided photos and key words of the captions for each video inspire me a lot.	0	5	7.5	62.5	25
6 English subtitles in each video are very useful for me.	0	0	62.5	17.5	20
7 The provided videos are more interesting and lively.	0	15	10	25	50
8 Videos help me practice English in the real contexts.	0	10	42.5	20	27.5
9 Videos help develop my critical thinking skill.	5	15	30	15	35
10 My vocabulary capacity increases a lot after watching videos.	0	0	37.5	42.5	20
11 I can remember English vocabulary more easily through video-based tasks.	0	0	15	37.5	47.5
12 I spent time learning English by watching videos provided by my teacher at home.	0	12,5	62,5	15	10

Apart from the findings of questionnaires, the data were collected from the interviews with five target students. On one hand, the interviewees admitted that English listening learning through video-based tasks helped solve the problem of boredom and the listening skill's natural challenge. In addition, applying video-based tasks in and outside classrooms encouraged the students to be more confident and responsible in their learning. They said that they could improve their listening skills through extensive online videos.

Besides, watching videos was very beneficial for the students where memorizing vocabulary was concerned. On the other hand, they showed that they were sometimes lazy to access to the Internet or download videos to watch at home because of the time constraint or the unavailability of the Internet, computers or smart phones. Moreover, they believed that their English listening level was not good enough to easily understand videos without being exposed to subtitles in each video or without the teacher's providing clues. They eventually showed their inability of choosing right videos fit for their level to watch extensively at home because there were a numerous range of online English videos.

5 DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Regarding to the obtained findings, it can be clearly observed that employing videos as a supporting instrument was demonstrated to positively and significantly foster the development of listening learning among HUFİ EFL students. The results reveal that the students were attracted and involved in videos to acquire listening skill. Almost all students agreed that exploring videos was helpful, and interesting. Moreover, they presented that this approach inspired them, interested them and helped increase their vocabulary ranges and motivation.

As a result, teachers should be responsible to help students become more conscious of the importance of videos in English learning. Students must understand clearly that being exposed to listening to a number of videos can bring them a lot of benefits such as expanding their vocabulary, improving pronunciation and developing listening, speaking and writing skills. In addition, videos materials can create opportunities for students to catch up with different English dialects or accents and speaking fluency. In other words, teachers should raise students' interest and motivation in listening learning with videos to make EFL teaching and learning better, and ultimately they could find ways to exploit most efficiently provided videos in the course-books.

On the other hand, the findings illustrates that implementing listening through video-based tasks ran into a few troubles. One problem concluded from the above findings is that a large majority of students did not notice the using of videos in their learning because they did not give any feedback at all, which shows neglect of videos. Moreover, the lack of attractiveness and liveliness in the given videos was indicated as well as most students could not improve their critical thinking skill. Thus in order to achieve listening targets among students' English learning syllabus goals of each course, these shown problems should be solved in some practical ways.

In other words, it is a must to recognize the factors that affect the success of videos besides other listening sources in teaching and learning English listening skill. When introducing a listening learning method related to videos, teachers initially need to make a decision on what videos should be chosen. Besides given videos by the publisher of textbooks, it is necessary for teachers to choose some more videos on related topics, and then teachers should identify whether videos are suitable enough for students' level. Also, whether videos are interesting, lively and motivated enough for the students to watch should be considered carefully. The last important thing is how watching videos can develop students' critical thinking; thus, teachers should design open questions for students to brainstorm after watching each video and make short presentations in class afterwards.

6 CONCLUSION

Overall, listening comprehension is one of the prerequisites contributing to oriented communication success in a language classroom. Among factors linked to this success, the application of video-based tasks have been considered and processed in HUFİ EFL courses thanks to its roles and benefits. Currently, there are a variety of online video materials, which opens up opportunities to enhance English listening teaching and learning for not only language teachers but also learners as well. This study was designed to satisfy the requirements regarding the listening skill set forth for the English teaching syllabus for non-English major students at HUFİ. The strategy of using video-based tasks is being pursued where the students can engage in both in-class activities and self-study at home. In fact, regarding listening skill, the students' learning motivation as well as other mentioned profits has been enhanced through carrying out tasks based on authentic videos, but nevertheless teachers interested in guiding students' listening through videos must choose suitable

and attractive video sources to enhance not the effectiveness of videos but the students' listening comprehension.

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